

Speaking the ‘right’ English: Attitudes and beliefs of Italian students towards ‘native sounding’ and foreign-accented English

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This study examines the language attitudes and beliefs of Italians towards ‘native’ and ‘non-native’ varieties of spoken English, with particular attention to the evaluation of their Italian accent. Semi-structured interviews were carried out while the participants (19 students in higher education) were studying abroad. These revealed a deep-seated belief that a ‘native-sounding’ accent is required in order to become truly proficient in the language and to be taken seriously, which caused a strong sense of anxiety and inadequacy in the respondents. The interviews touched upon multiple topics, including their interactions with others while abroad, their fear of being discriminated against, and their struggles with identity and self-positioning. However, the longitudinal nature of this study revealed that the time spent abroad ultimately contributed to changing their attitudes, making them more open towards their multilingualism and their own Italian-sounding accent, although they remained aware of the possible advantages that ‘sounding native’ provides.

Keywords: Foreign Accent; English as a Lingua Franca; ELF; English Language Teaching; Linguistic Insecurity; Language Attitudes; Native-Speakerism

1. Introduction

Teaching English today requires taking into account multiple variables: the learners’ future interlocutors, and whether they will be native speakers of English (NES) or, far more likely (see Crystal, 2012), non-native speakers (NNES); if the learner’s goal is to move abroad, either to a so-called Inner Circle country (Kachru, 1985) or to one of the many places in the world where English is spoken as a Lingua Franca (ELF); and in what circumstances the learner will use English—daily life, their education, or a specialised field.

Plenty of research has been carried out investigating how the ELF paradigm can be integrated with English Language Teaching (ELT), with the goal of “providing learners with tools to become effective communicators with English in its pluralized forms” (Vettorel and Lopriore, 2013, p. 484). However, a widespread idea persists which sees NES “as the ultimate models of language use and the ideal teachers of a language, thus invalidating, discriminating, and/or underestimating [NNES]” (Llurda & Calvet-Terré, 2024, p. 231). This

ideology, termed native-speakerism (Holliday, 2015), still seems to have a hold not only on teaching methods, but also on learners' minds. Indeed, an image of English as a 'property' of those born in the 'Inner Circle' appears to be widespread and deep-rooted among NNES, which results in the fact that 'acceptable' forms of English are still defined on the basis of adherence to the 'native' ideal. This seems to lead to a devaluation of 'non-native' users' abilities as multilingual speakers (Cook, 1991), as well as to increased anxiety and linguistic insecurity (Foo & Tan, 2019): indeed, as Cook (2002) underlined, hinging learners' goals on matching NES's idealised proficiency means imposing a single standardised model which rarely fits all learners' specific needs, and also putting NNES in a position of eternal disadvantage as "defective native speaker[s]" (ibid., p. 20).

Preliminary studies in the Italian context (Bagni, 2022; Newbold & Paschke, 2022) suggest that Italians might also be susceptible to this phenomenon, but limited research has been conducted thus far at a national level. Consequently, the aim of the present study was to investigate Italians' language attitudes towards 'native-sounding' English and foreign-accented—and specifically Italian-accented—English. Particular attention was devoted to observing whether the respondents saw the need to conform to a 'native' use of the language, especially accent-wise, and why; and if this might foster any feelings of anxiety or inadequacy.

2. Background

The distinction between 'native' and 'non-native' speakers has long been used by both linguists and non-experts as a way to define themselves and others, as it is seemingly extremely simple. The native speaker is supposedly recognised as such by 'birthright' (McArthur, 1998), i.e., having acquired the mother tongue from birth; this figure is opposed to those who have instead learned that same language later in life, a process considered inferior to birthright regardless of the user's ability. Thus, a binary classification supposedly divides 'native speakers' and 'non-native speakers'. Nonetheless, the concept of 'birthright', by itself, is not sufficient to define 'nativeness': Hackert (2012) describes how 'Outer Circle' English users are frequently excluded from 'nativeness' despite having acquired the language from birth because "[their] competence differs perceptibly from that of native speakers of what has been called 'the traditional bases of English,' i.e., British or American English" (ibid., p. 11). 'Standard English' is thus "an abstracted, idealised, homogenous model" (Lippi-Green, 2012, p. 67) pertaining to the 'Inner circle' alone, despite the great variation that can be found there as well.

Indeed, 'nativeness' does not correspond to a language model with precise characteristics that can be analysed syntactically or phonetically. Nonetheless,

the NES remains as a reference point in both language teaching and assessment, and varieties of English pertaining to the 'Inner Circle' are still perceived as the 'correct' standards to teach and learn worldwide. While there have been efforts to foreground practical language use instead of the imitation of the 'native' model in ELT (see e.g., Seidlhofer & Widdowson, 2020), 'passing' for a 'native speaker' persists as a reference point to measure achievement (Piller, 2002). This causes "a severe self-confidence problem" (Llurda, 2009, p. 97) for NNES: for example, Dewaele and McCloskey (2015, p. 236) observed that highly proficient multilingual speakers "disliked FA [foreign accent] significantly more, especially their own FA, possibly because of their own higher expectations." It seems possible to observe this phenomenon in terms of linguistic insecurity, i.e., "speakers' feeling that the variety they use is somehow inferior, ugly or bad" (Meyerhoff, 2006, p. 292) compared to another dominant, 'correct' variety (Lippi-Green, 2012).

While these matters are receiving considerable attention internationally, research on these topics is still quite limited in the Italian context. Thus, the aim of this study was to investigate the language attitudes—the set of evaluations formed about others on the basis of accent and language use (see Dragojevic et al., 2021)—held by Italians towards English spoken with different accents, both 'native' and 'non-native'.

3. Method

3.1. Participants

19 respondents took part in this study: they were students in higher education (including at the doctoral level) between 18 and 35 years old, who have Italian as their L1. Snowball sampling was used to identify potential candidates. Inclusion criteria required them to have a self-reported proficiency level equivalent to at least a B1 on the CEFR scale, so as to ensure that no participants were complete beginners in the study of English. Moreover, in order to ensure that the respondents would have enough experience with interacting with different varieties of English, and with using the language in a wide range of contexts, the selection criteria required them to be taking part in a Study Abroad (SA) experience at the time of the interview. The stay would need to have just begun, and to last for a minimum of three months, so that the participants could be interviewed at two different times. The aim of this longitudinal design was to observe whether the experience abroad would somehow affect their language attitudes.

An active effort was made to record experiences that were as varied as possible: great attention was thus paid to ensure diversity among participants regarding their gender, age, proficiency level, amount of previous experiences abroad, geographical origin, and fields of study. This level of variation was

deemed to be of great importance to the present study, since it would allow to verify the possible existence of a widespread language ideology that is not dependent on a specific background. Participants' information can be observed in detail in Table 1.

Table 1
Participants' Information

Name	Sex	Age	Education	Subject area	Proficiency	SA destination
EU1	F	20	BA student	Political Sciences	C1	Sweden
EU2	F	31	PhD student	History	B2	Sweden
EU3	M	24	MA student	Philosophy	C1	Germany
EU4	F	25	PhD student	Italian literature	B1	France
EU5	M	20	BA student	Computer science	B2	Sweden
EU6	M	22	MA student	Computer science	C1	Sweden
EU7	F	23	MA student	Engineering management	B1	Spain
EU8	M	26	MA student	Digital games	C2	Malta
EU9	M	24	PhD student	Physics	B1	Germany
IR1	F	19	BA student	Criminology	B2+	Ireland
IR2	F	24	PhD student	Italian literature	C1	Ireland
IR3	F	27	PhD student	Geography	B1/B2	Ireland
IR4	F	22	BA student	Foreign languages	C1	Ireland
IR5	F	29	PhD student	Italian literature	C1	Ireland
UK1	F	21	BA student	Fashion design	B2	Scotland, UK
UK2	F	20	BA student	Foreign languages	C1	England, UK
UK3	F	25	PhD student	Italian linguistics	B2	England, UK
UK4	F	26	PhD student	English linguistics	C2	England, UK
UK5	F	24	MA student	Cultural heritage education	C1	Scotland, UK

The participants came from 10 cities in 9 different regions, spanning the entire Italian peninsula. However, due to the personal nature of their interviews, their cities of origin are not reported in order to ensure their privacy. Conversely, the Table shows their SA destinations: 9 interviewees were staying in non-Anglophone European countries, where they still needed to use English as a lingua franca on a daily basis; 5 were staying in Ireland, while 5 more were staying in the United Kingdom. Special attention was devoted to selecting an equal number of participants studying abroad in Anglophone and non-Anglophone countries, since it was hypothesised that the different SA destination might represent a relevant factor influencing the respondents' attitudes: for instance, those staying in Anglophone destinations would be far more likely to interact with 'native' speakers, and with a local 'native' accent.

3.2. Procedure

Semi-structured interviews were employed in order to elicit information directly about the respondents' beliefs, thoughts and feelings on this topic, and

to try and reconstruct how their attitudes had come to be (Karatsareas, 2022). The interview guide included 23 open-ended questions, modified from a pilot study which had been carried out in the previous year (see Cigliano, 2025), designed to explore the respondents' attitudes towards English in general, and ELF in particular; towards 'native speakers' and 'non-native speakers'; towards foreign-accented English; and towards their experience with ELT in the Italian context. The present article will report the results concerning the participants' attitudes and beliefs towards 'native-sounding' English and 'Italian-sounding' English.

The interviews took place between October 2024 and June 2025, with an average distance of four months between the first interview and the follow-up. They were performed either online or in person depending on the availability and location of the participants at the time. They were carried out in Italian, to avoid creating the impression that the participants' L2 abilities were being 'assessed', and consequently fostering feelings of anxiety that could hinder an open and spontaneous discussion (see García-Ponce et al., 2018; Karatsareas, 2022). All excerpts from the interviews cited here were translated by the author.

The interviews lasted on average one hour, with the shortest being 40 minutes and the longest 1 hour and 48 minutes. The total recording time of the interviews—both the first and second one—amounts to 38 hours and 9 minutes. The audio of the interviews was recorded with the informed consent of the participants, both oral and written; the recordings were then transcribed verbatim and analysed using multiple methods: Thematic Analysis (TA), which allows to identify and analyse patterns of meaning in a text corpus (Braun & Clarke, 2006); Positioning Theory, to observe "the discursive process whereby selves are located in conversations as observably and subjectively coherent participants in jointly produced story lines" (Davies & Harré, 1990, p. 49); and a selection of tools from the field of Conversation Analysis, following Laihonen (2008) and Liebscher and Dailey-O'Cain (2009), in order to foreground how, during an interview, "talk about language is constructed to meet the expectations of the question, the general orientation of the interview and the amount of shared knowledge" (Laihonen, 2008, p. 678).

4. Results and discussion

Accent was a highly discussed topic, to the point that there was almost no need to prompt the respondents to share their views about it: in the majority of cases, they mentioned it from the very beginning. It was most often to provide a description of their new SA environment, in which local or unfamiliar accents were especially prominent, but it also emerged when talking about past teachers, current colleagues, or their own perceived difficulties and abilities. In

particular, 'native' accents were the most frequently discussed, alongside the Italian one.

4.1. Sounding 'native' as a sign of skill

Despite this attention to accent, when the participants were asked to describe what it meant, in their opinion, to be proficient English speakers, they initially assigned greater importance to intelligibility and correct pronunciation in broader terms: only three respondents explicitly included having a NES-like accent among their requirements for 'speaking English well'. Nonetheless, many described it as a 'bonus': something that could 'wow' the interlocutor, and crucially, indicate that the learner had put in special effort to 'master' English in all its parts. Indeed, despite the little relevance initially ascribed to 'native-like' accent, the respondents' narratives soon revealed their underlying attitudes towards 'native' and 'non-native' accents. It should be noted that many respondents had not been aware of their attitudes until they were directly prompted to reflect on these matters: multiple participants changed the description of their beliefs mid-interview, often realising that they attributed greater importance to sounding 'native-like' than they had originally thought.

Most respondents had never reflected on this matter before the interview, and thus needed to develop their own definition of 'speaking good English' on the spot. For this reason, some uncertainty was to be expected; nonetheless, it is striking to see how often a NES-like accent was at the forefront of their minds, even when it was not deemed to be a necessary skill, or it contradicted their previously expressed beliefs about language learning and proficiency (cf. García-Ponce et al., 2018).

If you meet someone who can maybe speak well, but has a marked accent, perhaps the first thing you think is, "well, they're a second-rate speaker." I don't know if anyone thinks that about me when I speak here. I don't know [laughs]. But since it's the first thing you hear . . . maybe we tend to categorize skill based on accent? . . . That's something I look at right away. But then actually, when I think about it, I say, you can also have an accent that is distinctly, I don't know, Italian, but if I'm saying things grammatically in the correct manner, I'm using the right words, I mean, you're speaking well. (Extract 1 - Interviewee UK4)

Multiple respondents followed a similar pattern to UK4: they first expressed a strong preference towards NES-like accents, then reflected on the greater importance of other skills (e.g. correct syntax in the extract above) in defining a proficient speaker. Nonetheless, many still sought to develop a 'native-like' accent (most often an American or British one), giving as a reason their

“perfectionism”: this further suggested that they believed NES-sounding accent to correspond to the highest level of language proficiency—one that they often believed to be unreachable:

I try very hard to . . . to imitate them [NES] when they speak. I mean, to try to absorb as much as possible of what they say and how they say it . . . think it's a bit- a bit of a personal expectation . . . that I have towards myself, you know? Because . . . I believe, perhaps a little naively, that . . . they speak English at a level . . . that I will never be able to reach. (Extract 2 - Interviewee UK2)

Even though it was frequently believed to be an ‘impossible’ goal, the respondents still sought to acquire one, since having an accent that was perceivably influenced by their L1 was seen as a sign of poor linguistic abilities. The word choices concerning this topic are striking, as they often described their Italian accent as “dirty,” “contaminating” the English language:

I've always liked the idea of having an accent, um . . . let's say English . . . Precisely because I admire and love this language so much that, um, I would like it not to be contaminated by my Italian side. (Extract 3 - Interviewee IR4)

The idea was widespread among respondents that any contact between different languages was to be taken as a mistake—whether that be L1 interference on the level of syntax or pronunciation, intentional code-switching, or a ‘non-native’ accent. In the respondents’ minds, ‘native’, monolingual English represented an “unmarked case” (Ellis, 2006), meaning that the use of a singular language at the time is considered not only as ‘standard’ but as ‘normal’. Thus, not being English-monolingual ‘by default’ makes learners automatically ‘faulty’ or ‘defective’ (cf. Cook, 2002). Consequently, some respondents shared the belief that the only way to become truly ‘good at English’, i.e., truly ‘native-like’, was to abandon their L1 entirely, substituting it with the L2.

While this was seen as somewhat extreme, the majority of participants believed in the importance of making a conscious effort to learn English and ‘get rid’ of the Italian accent. Thus, discussion describing a ‘native-like’ accent as a sign of greater language ability was often accompanied by a concurrent description of L2 users who had not acquired one not only as unskilled, but as “lazy”:

There's also the typical stereotype of the Italian person who doesn't feel like learning languages, and so . . . I mean they don't even try to improve

themselves maybe . . . I think that the mindset of many Italians is “whatever, I make myself understood” and then, I mean, it doesn’t matter, “I use the English I have, it’s not like I improve.” (Extract 4 - Interviewee EU1)

From EU1’s words, it is clear that successful communication—“making oneself understood”—is not enough: many respondents repeatedly stated that speaking English ‘for real’ means something different, in which a NES-like accent have a prominent role. It is not surprising, then, that most respondents identified ‘successful’ English learners among their acquaintances mostly on the basis of their ‘native-like’ accent.

However, most respondents provided a description of their Italian co-nationals as generally ‘bad at English’, usually due to their distinctive accent. It was often accompanied by a depiction of them as not only ‘incompetent and lazy, but “localist” and “provincial” as well. Indeed, it has long been observed how ‘deviation’ from the standard language can index negative extralinguistic features: as Mugglestone (2003) notes, images of ‘elegance’, ‘decorum’ and ‘propriety’, as well as ‘vulgarity’ or ‘impropriety’ can be linked to specific accents, making them a reflection of the speaker’s presupposed inner qualities. Thus, the L2 user’s ‘foreign’ accent does not only carry assumptions about geographical origin or linguistic competence, but also about intelligence, education, and even moral characteristics (Garrett, 2007).

Consequently, when the respondents expressed feelings of anxiety at the thought of needing to speak English, these were not only due to apprehension regarding the correctness of their language use: they mostly had to do with anxiety over what kind of self-image they would project to others. Thus, even the respondents who had initially described a positive attitude towards an Italian-sounding accent later expressed the desire to develop a ‘native-like’ accent, in order to gain a material advantage (e.g., in the job market), to integrate in the host country, and crucially, to avoid negative interactions.

4.2. Becoming ‘native-like’: ‘Passing’ as a social advantage

Despite the fact that developing a ‘native-like’ accent is traditionally seen as a reflection of ultimate attainment, the concept of ‘passing’—i.e., being mistaken for a NES—is often considered an almost impossible feat, especially for those who did not acquire the language in childhood. However, as she observed the experiences of people who had moved abroad, Piller (2002) theorised that ‘passing’ might be a temporary performance instead of a permanent change, which individuals decide to ‘put on’ in certain situations and for a limited amount of time, in order to gain a certain advantage. In that case, the process hinges on the L2 users’ sociolinguistic awareness of when it is advantageous or

disadvantageous to 'pass': thus, 'passing' becomes a (mostly) conscious decision on their part, which might be motivated by different factors.

Further discussion during the interviews revealed how many respondents believed the development of a 'native-like' accent to be extremely important in order to increase their appeal in the eyes of potential employers. Notably, this was not only to 'distinguish themselves' from other candidates purely in terms of language skills: many respondents saw a NES-like accent almost as a requirement to work in certain contexts. A 'native' accent was often characterised as "cleaner" and "more professional" than a 'non-native' one, reflecting the prestige attributed to it. Notably, this view was also shared by those who did not insist on the necessity of having a 'native-sounding' accent to be considered proficient speakers: they remarked how the need for passing as NES was situational, like EU4 below, and it mostly applied to professional or academic situations, associated with a high level of formality.

In informal conversation it's not something that would bother me [having an Italian accent], right, I wouldn't pay any attention to it . . . For reasons of professionalism, I would like to have it as clean as possible, because we're already talking about terms that are perhaps more technical, more specific, so I would like it not to be affected by anything. (Extract 5 - Interviewee EU4)

The need to develop a NES-like accent to integrate in the workforce was indeed an expectation for most participants, albeit one which rarely had roots in their direct experience, as most of them were full-time students. This might be even more telling: the idea that standard, 'native-sounding' English would be a requirement in the workplace had become an unquestioned certainty (albeit a justified one: cf. studies regarding negative attitudes towards employees speaking 'nonstandard' varieties, e.g., Levon et al., 2021; Lippi-Green, 1997, 2012). Many respondents envisioned the same situation: a nondescript office setting where a NES would be preferred for the job not due to their language competence, in general, but to their 'nativeness' and accent.

If you're doing a job interview for a company . . . they need someone . . . a formal person, so someone who has studied, who has learned . . . and so . . . there's one person, a native English speaker, and then there is a . . . a Chinese person who has studied in England for twenty years, but like it or not, he has his accent. And so I think that in that case it's going to be preferred who- on the level of- with equal everything, CV . . . experience and all, I believe that's going to be preferred who has this English that's much cleaner and much more . . . I don't want to say understandable, because going back to what I said before, if- if you can speak it, if you can

make yourself understood, it doesn't matter what accent you have. But I think that in some very formal situations, having a . . . an accent- a good accent is important. (Extract 6 - Interviewee UK1)

A “good” (i.e., ‘native’) accent was consistently attributed greater prestige than the Italian one when it came to formal situations. This attitude was shared in particular by PhD candidates, as they had direct experience with using English in formal contexts (e.g., conferences, or during SA). However, the interviews revealed how the advantages of sounding ‘native’ were frequently seen to expand to other contexts as well:

[This] hasn't happened to me, I haven't had any experiences. but I don't want it to happen in the future, I don't want to . . . let's say . . . close any doors, have doors closed, whether it's job interviews or even just acquaintances, because I might not be . . . considered for what I can be, or I might be . . . discriminated as someone who . . . is not educated, who does not have a good level of English, and things like that. (Extract 7 - Interviewee EU5)

EU5's discussion revealed how English language skills can index characteristics such as intelligence or education level, beyond language proficiency in itself; this is in line with Martín Rojo's (2019) observations that today, knowledge of English is linked to personal traits such as self-responsibility and professional worth. Language learning thus becomes “a dedicated investment in self development,” even “a professional morality,” and “a lack of which would indicate less initiative and commitment and invite questioning, doubt, distrust, or even contempt” (Gao & Park, 2015, p. 87).

Moreover, while some respondents cited above distinguished between the use of ‘native-sounding’ English in professional contexts, where it was seen as ‘necessary’, and informal situations where their NNES accent could be accepted, here EU5 highlighted how using a ‘non-native’ accent might constitute a disadvantage for personal relationships too. Indeed, the respondents often feared to be excluded or discriminated against due to their accent betraying their foreignness and ‘otherness’. It comes to little surprise, then, that they would often try to pass as NES in informal settings as well, converging towards the ‘native’ accent of their interlocutors—sometimes even subconsciously, as in the case of EU3 below:

When I used to spend a lot of time with British people I had a more British accent, but instead if I'm with international people or like with Americans, I have a much more American accent . . . I'm not saying that I make an effort to cover up my Italian accent etcetera, but it's like I

unconsciously . . . it bothers me to sound like a foreigner, that's all.
(Extract 8 - Interviewee EU3)

In those instances, it seems that EU3's accent converged towards his interlocutors' ones in order to minimise social distance, reflecting a desire for social approval and acceptance (Giles et al., 1991). This process is not limited to 'native' accents, but the employment of this type of 'strategy' to integrate in the host country was mostly mentioned by those staying in Ireland and the UK. Indeed, there was a fundamental difference with the group of respondents staying in non-Anglophone countries: as EU1 remarked, "since English is not the official language here [in Sweden], if I speak English, regardless of how well I speak it, it is still obvious that I am a foreigner." Moreover, the issue of integration was most often brought up by those participants who would spend a longer period abroad, as was partially to be expected.

Quite often, however, more than a positive desire to integrate into the local environment, it was the negative feeling of being perceived as 'different' or foreign that drove the respondents' desire to develop a local or otherwise 'native' English accent. Those who did not sound 'native-like' frequently felt a sense of unease and inadequacy, which affected even those who strongly expressed no desire to change their Italian accent, and who did not seem to associate 'native' accents to language skills. For instance, IR5 initially described how she did not aim to develop a NES-like accent, because her goal was "simply to . . . be intelligible, so to make myself understood by the people who live here {in Ireland};" during her interview, she defined 'ultimate attainment' uniquely on the basis of intelligibility and fluency. However, during her interview she recounted how, in multiple occasions during her first month of SA, she had felt judged by NES due to her Italian accent. For instance, as IR5 described her anxiety when having to speak English, she mentioned how it frequently occurred in conversation with NES, regardless of the situation:

INT: why do you think that is?

IR5: because . . . you really feel the pressure of having to . . . prove that you're fluent in the language . . . because you see that they look at you strangely if you make a mistake, if you use it incorrectly. so you feel . . . it's as if you feel like you're an object of observation in part.
(Extract 9 - Interviewee IR5)

Of the two groups of respondents, those staying in Anglophone countries reported feeling a strong external pressure to conform to the 'native' standard more often than their counterparts staying in other EU countries. On the contrary, the latter often became increasingly more relaxed as time went on, a feeling usually fostered by the fact that their social networks while abroad

were mostly composed of other international, 'non-native' English speakers. The result was a situation of linguistic parity, as was described by EU5:

I feel more . . . on a more equal footing with people who, well, make a few small mistakes or something, but you can see they're making an effort and trying to speak English . . . because I can relate to them, I mean, I know that- I know what it's like, so I'm perhaps even more understanding . . . I might wait for them to finish their sentence, and they do the same with me. (Extract 10 - Interviewee EU5)

While others did not describe feeling pressured to change their way of speaking to the extent experienced by IR5 (see also Extract 13 below), many participants in both groups still expressed analogous feelings of unease and anxiety whenever they were 'recognised' as Italians while abroad: it was a frequently discussed issue, as it similarly forced them to reflect on their identity, how it was perceived by others, and what they actually wanted to convey to their interlocutors.

At a preliminary level, for many, the fact of being 'recognised' as Italians was equivalent to a negative judgement regarding their language skills, as it meant that their accent was so strong that it could be noticed as soon as they began speaking. However, as was discussed above, it also represented the risk to be stereotyped or excluded, and even a loss of control over how they expressed their identity. This feeling was described as upsetting by multiple respondents, in both destination groups. EU3, in particular, showed great apprehension about this possibility:

If I'm having a conversation I don't want to be like flattened on the fact that I come from a certain place, right? but I just want to exchange ideas. and . . . and not be, right, not have- not have a [label] stuck on me- if I have a neutral accent, people have to ask me, "where are you from?" and if I want to I'll tell them. (Extract 11 - Interviewee EU3)

His interview reveals that at the heart of the matter lies agency: the discussion is hinged on what he 'wants', a verb repeated multiple times—"I don't want to be flattened," "if I want to I'll tell them," "I could lie if I wanted to," "I'm the one who decides what information I want to give you," "I want to be the one to manage . . ." In her research, Piller (2002) notes that the performance of passing is often employed in a very specific interactional context, i.e., when meeting new people for the first time. People do not wish to be recognised immediately as foreigners or as coming from a certain country, because they prefer "not to be reduced to their original national identities" (*ibid.*, p. 194). In EU3's case, it appears that by being recognised not as a person in his own right,

but as a generic 'Italian', he was also positioned as such and attributed a series of characteristics that he felt to be inexact—especially regarding L2 proficiency. Indeed, the respondents were not the only one to express criticism over Italians' English language skills. Many interviewees reported being complimented for their 'surprisingly good' proficiency, both by NES and other EU citizens, who believed that being 'good at English' was somewhat unexpected from Italians:

Something that often happens to me when I'm abroad, also here that I'm here in Scotland, is that when I speak English people compliment me. They say, "you don't sound Italian," meaning you can't hear the accent, right? . . . I mean, there's a bit of a Super Mario-like perception, right? people expect an Italian speaking in English to be automatically, "well! what a beautiful day!" [with a strong, stereotypical Italian accent] . . . right? And when you don't have that [laughs] automatically, am I right? it's just "wow." (Extract 12 - Interviewee UK5)

From UK5's description, it appears that a stereotypical, strong, 'Super Mario' accent was seemingly expected of most Italians, and not having one constituted an explicit exception. Both the respondents and the people with whom they interacted abroad seemed to have a clear image of Italians as poor speakers of English—one that was rarely challenged by the respondents themselves. Similar comments were received by multiple participants: they were meant as compliments by those who uttered them, and interestingly, they were accepted as such; nonetheless, they still had a deep impact on the respondents' self-image and positioning. Those instances were remembered clearly by the interviewees, and usually reported in the form of constructed dialogue: "you speak great English for being Italian" (EU3), "oh wow, you speak English very well for an Italian" (EU8), "you know English well, your Italian peers know it less than you do" (IR2), "but you're fluent, I wouldn't have thought you're Italian" (UK1). This expectation, held by both NES and NNES alike, of Italians speaking mostly a heavily accented, "macaronic" English is in line with previous research (e.g., Aiello, 2018; Faez, 2011). A similar view had previously emerged from the pilot study, whereby Italians were seen as traditionally 'bad at English', and those Italians who had become fluent L2 users were 'exceptional', and even seen as 'less Italian' than others (Cigliano, 2025). In the current research, the comments and feedback that the participants received during their SA often contributed to reinforcing the stereotypical image of Italians as 'poor English speakers'; even when NES showed appreciation for the respondents' Italian accent, they defined it as "cute" at best, thus still undermining the credibility of the respondents (Hermans & Sloep, 2018)—a treatment that did not seem to be shared by other northern European accents, which were less recognisable. Unsurprisingly, then, only a minority of

respondents reported an explicit wish to keep their Italian accent—whether it be because they had given up on changing it, or because they had strong positive ties to their national identity. Conversely, many others described an active effort to ‘pass’ for a ‘native speaker’. This process, however, was not painless: IR5 went as far as to describe it as ‘violent’:

Which is the right variety [of English]? In my opinion there’s no longer a variety- it shouldn’t, at least on an abstract level, exist a variety . . . because then it becomes . . . deep down it’s racist . . . But . . . on a rational level, I say these things, and I believe them. But then I know that, like, subconsciously I feel, when I talk to my [NES] housemates, that something is wrong . . . It’s as if . . . there’s this norm, about language, and I must . . . conform to the way the person from here speaks it. So my identity, which is different . . . which is culturally different, has to be suppressed when I speak English. so the fact that I have a different inflection . . . to be fully integrated into that culture, I have to get rid of it. I mean, I see it as a form of violence. But then . . . it’s true, I mean, on a subconscious level even when I was in Italy, when I listened to a friend of mine speaking with a perfect American accent, I said, “Ah, she speaks English very well,” when perhaps I can speak it at the same level, except that I don’t have that accent . . .and what’s the difference? (Extract 13 - Interviewee IR5)

The negative interactions described by IR5 had a deep effect on her: she had initially shown appreciation for her destination, a multilingual and multicultural city, where she could frequently hear different accents, and she had initially rejected the notion of a single (‘native’) standard to imitate. It is interesting to note how she explicitly addressed the difference between what she believed in, rationally, and how she felt.

This is in line with the traditional structure of language attitudes, which are seen as ‘composed’ of cognition, affect and behaviour. In his overview of the subject, Garrett (2010) underlines how there are occasions when these components seem not to be aligned, as in IR5’s case. Thus, while on a cognitive level she seemed to think that it is ‘not right’ to demand that someone change their accent, her beliefs were challenged by the negative feelings that she experienced in interaction. Nonetheless, her positive attitude towards ‘native-sounding’ accent seemingly predated her SA experience, and was described as ‘subconscious’. Indeed, it is important to note that while participants might show a preference for ‘native-like’ accents, or even consciously try to develop one, they were rarely aware of the social dynamics of prestige underlying their choices and attitudes. To them, sounding ‘native’ often simply meant speaking English as one ‘is supposed to’: it was a matter of ‘common sense’.

4.3. The myth of the neutral accent: Attitudes towards NNEST

Indeed, not only are 'native' accents believed to be the most 'correct' ones: they are also believed to be neutral, i.e., the natural, 'normal' way to speak the language. NES are thus often believed to 'sound neutral', even though a neutral accent does not exist; yet, its 'myth' seems to be deeply rooted in the collective consciousness (Moyer, 2013). The perceived 'neutrality' of 'native-like' accent is only produced by the fact that one specific way of speaking has been attributed the status of 'standard', and thus all other accents are understood and defined on the basis of their difference from it (Lippi-Green, 2012).

The possibility to develop a 'neutral' accent was mentioned multiple times by the interviewees, including IR5, who saw it as a possible escape from being treated as 'other'. It should be noted that it is virtually impossible to have no accent at all, either in one's first language or especially when learning a second one. Still, the search for a 'neutral' accent by multiple respondents suggests that they were aware of the stigmatisation of 'non-native' accents, and tried to avoid it by 'reducing' theirs, especially as the Italian accent was specifically seen a mark of poor skills. The desire to 'dampen' their accent and replace it with a 'neutral' one was also shared by those participants who rejected the idea of sounding more 'native-like': they did not seem to realise that a 'neutral' accent is just a 'native' accent in disguise. However, there might be further possible explanations for why they would rather seek a non-existent, 'neutral' accent rather than a specific, geographically-bound 'native' one. In particular, it can be inferred that the preference for a 'neutral' accent might be due to the respondents' keen awareness that adopting a 'native', and thus localised accent could have direct consequences on their self-image and identity. Indeed, Moyer (2013) underlines how "[accent] socially and psychologically situates the speaker in terms of group belonging and affirms personal identity and stance in an immediate way" (p. 11). For the respondents, then, the matter was not only about choosing an accent: it was about selecting an identity to display during SA. Indeed, identity is not a fixed, monolithic concept; recent ethnographically-oriented sociolinguistic approaches view identity as constructed in linguistic interaction, and thus highly dependent on the social context and the interlocutors (Blackledge & Pavlenko, 2001). The experience abroad foregrounded how an identity usually taken for granted by the respondents, their Italian one, was now made visible and salient in the new context, through language use in general, and accent in particular. The choice was thus between 'keeping' the Italian identity, which marked the participants as foreigners through the highly recognisable accent; or moving towards a 'native-like' identity and accent. A fictitious 'neutral' accent might thus have represented a way to bypass this dilemma, as it would allow them not to desert their Italian identity, while taking advantage of the increased prestige given by not sounding explicitly 'non-native'.

However, this perception of ‘native’ accents as neutral risks to reinforce the perception that L2 users should unquestioningly adopt a ‘native-like’ accent—despite the difficulties and frustration that this endeavour entails—because it is ‘common sense’ that one should do so. The corpus already reveals how the respondents—themselves ‘non-native’ speakers of English—often harshly criticised other NNEST for their ‘non-nativeness’. This was most frequently noticeable when it came to descriptions of Italian teachers of English: the respondents were often dissatisfied with the perceived language abilities of their NNEST, and especially with their ‘non-native’ accents, which were often mentioned as proxy to describe their overall inadequacy. Conversely, ‘native’ teachers were frequently believed to have an intrinsic value, as they allowed learners to come into contact with the ‘real English language’; this is in line with a native-speakerist ideology (Holliday, 2005; Llorca & Calvet-Terré, 2024). Numerous studies have highlighted how ‘native’ speakers are still considered to be more reliable users—and thus, teachers—of English (e.g., Ba Doan, 2016; Llorca, 2004), which Holliday (2015) describes as a form of linguistic imperialism still present “at the core of the idealisation and promotion of teachers who are constructed as native-speakers” (p. 12). While in certain cases, research has highlighted how there can coexist appreciation for both NEST and NNEST, recognising their different strengths (see e.g., Achmad et al., 2024), the respondents of the present study mostly seemed critical of the abilities of their Italian teachers of English—with very few exceptions, which ultimately reinforced the idea that truly skilled Italian users of English are somewhat ‘exceptional’. In general terms, NEST were seen as having a separate role from the Italian language instructors: while the latter dealt with grammar and ‘rules’, ‘native’ teachers promoted learners’ progress, and specifically their speaking and listening skills. Their accent was their key strength, which was often seen as more important even than their teaching skills:

If you put like a hooligan in charge of teaching, apart from the security issues that there’d be, the fact that he’d probably come to school drunk, but if you take that away it’s still better than having an Italian teacher with a degree . . . but especially when . . . when you’re little, simply having a bit of habit, of context, someone who speaks to you in that language . . . in my opinion it’s much much better than . . . than like having lessons in Italian or Italian teachers who speak English . . . often badly. (Extract 14 - Interviewee EU3)

Similarly, others commented on the advantage of having a NEST because students would be able to absorb their ‘correct’ accent:

Even if it’s just a grammar lesson, if a native speaker is teaching it to you, you’re still unconsciously and unknowingly listening to a native speaker

... having a native-speaking teacher, not someone who's reached C2 level, but someone who was born and raised there, in England for example, I think that's much better, radically better. (Extract 15 - Interviewee UK2)

The respondents seemed to have fully assimilated the dominant language ideology that sees 'nativeness' as setting the language standard—as a model, as a goal for learners, and as the most prestigious variety—thus devaluing the learners' own way of speaking in the process, becoming complicit in the propagation of the dominant (native-speakerist) language ideology “against themselves, their own interests and identities” (Lippi-Green, 2012, p. 68; emphasis added). This became apparent when in the description of their NNEST, their 'Italianness' itself began to be mentioned as an inconvenience. Even when the respondents described positive interactions with NNEST, their skills were presented as somewhat 'unexpected', similarly to the comments that they received while abroad described in Section 4.2.

My middle school teacher too, even though she was very Italian, but like she was brilliant, she taught me a lot, but she was very Italian. (Extract 16 - Interviewee UK4)

The use of adversative conjunctions and concessive clauses is abundant in the description of 'talented' Italian teachers, who are always good despite their origin and 'non-nativeness'. These descriptions reinforce the theory that respondents might see proficiency and the Italian, 'non-native' identity as an oxymoron, inherently incompatible. This attitude clearly affected their perception of their peers and themselves, as well as their self-positioning in relation to their identity as English users, leaving them to choose between trying and pass for a NES, thus shedding their national identity and running the risk of being 'found out' at any turn, or accepting their status as “failed native speakers” (Cook, 1999, p. 185) from the start. However, the follow-up interviews revealed a partial shift away from the 'native' model.

4.4. The impact of using English firsthand: SA as a catalyst for attitude change

A second interview was carried out three to six months after the first. It used a modified version of the interview script, in order to prompt the respondents to reflect on possible changes in attitudes and beliefs that may have occurred as a result of their SA.

The follow-up revealed that most participants had progressively attributed less importance to sounding 'native-like', which had in turn contributed to reducing their negative feelings regarding speaking English as an L2. This change had seemingly occurred more quickly for those in non-Anglophone

countries, as was already suggested in Section 4.2: for these respondents in particular, English had been a ‘neutral’ tool that they had used to realise themselves and attain their goals; in a way, they had had a chance to ‘forget’ that there was a (supposed) reference point, i.e., the ‘native speaker’. However, at times this seemed to cause a discrepancy between the affective component of language attitudes and the cognitive one: while the respondents felt more at ease and more accepting of ELF, they remained aware that a ‘native-like’ accent has high prestige, and could constitute an asset in the job market:

I think I still want to go in that direction [developing a NES-like accent], to be honest, but for a reason which, in my opinion, is that the world in general is still fixated on having the right accent, the right pronunciation. so- moreover, the stereotype we Italians have is that as soon as they hear an Italian trying to speak English . . . it’s taken a little like someone who isn’t very competent even in their own field. for reasons of, mainly, survival, yes, I would still aim to try and get rid of the accent as much as possible. (Extract 17 - Interviewee EU5)

It is interesting to notice how their motivation had progressively shifted away from an unquestioning acceptance that sounding ‘native’ is the only way to speak English ‘properly’, and towards a critical understanding of the socioeconomic ramifications of speaking in a certain way. Thus, they could separate a ‘native-like’ accent with more ease from the concept of proficiency and ultimate attainment, like EU5 did: it was no longer him, but “the world in general” that is “fixated on having the right accent.”

Similarly, many of those who were in non-Anglophone countries, but also in Ireland and Scotland, believed that their ‘non-native’ use of English was ‘fine’ only as long as they were not in England: there, many believed, it could more easily happen that someone would comment on how English is ‘supposed to be spoken’, as the English were perceived to be ‘closed-off’ and hostile towards those who did not speak the language ‘properly’.

Before the period abroad, the majority of respondents had shown a great level of adherence to the Standard English Ideology—of course, without being aware of it at all: to them, the fact that ‘native’ English was beautiful, clean, proper and desirable (while ‘non-native’ English was ugly, dirty, macaronic and best avoided) was an obvious fact of life, simply ‘explained’ by common sense. Afterwards, however, they began to doubt that it was truly so: they appeared to have become aware of their past beliefs, and to have noticed that an alternative was possible—namely, being proficient without being ‘native-like’. While NES’ authority persisted, it appears that it was not unwittingly assigned to them by the respondents: on the contrary, they stressed that it was natives who claimed this position of authority for themselves. The respondents

recognised that 'passing' would be advantageous in England, but this push to conform did not come from within anymore: it was explicitly attributed to the pressure exerted by some 'natives' in particular. Perhaps optimistically, this could be interpreted as the first step in challenging and potentially 'dethroning' the 'native speaker'.

5. Conclusion

The work presented here is part of a broader research project which aims to shed some light on the attitudes and beliefs held by Italian users of English, and how those might influence their use of the language itself. Extensive interviews with students in higher education revealed how, at the beginning of their SA experience, the respondents perceived there to be only one 'correct' accent, i.e., the 'native' one, while being recognisable as Italians was often taken to index a general lack of language proficiency, regardless of the actual level of the speaker. In particular, the fact of being recognised as Italians while abroad often created great apprehension in the respondents due to the lack of control over their identity that this implied, and to fear of being discriminated against or stereotyped. The respondents showed great awareness of the prestige of a 'native-like' accent, which they often accepted unquestioningly, and was diametrically opposed to "dirty" and stigmatised 'non-native' accents, in particular their own Italian one. This caused in them feelings of anxiety and self-doubt, and created a friction between their identity as Italians and their self-positioning as skilled English users. In particular, they exhibited strong native-speakerist ideas, which often emerged in relation to their co-national peers and teachers. Nonetheless, the time spent abroad actively using the L2 seemed to cause a progressive shift away from this state of unwitting linguistic subordination and insecurity, as they realised the power dynamics underlying language use and began to partially challenge them.

While the period abroad seemed to have a powerful effect on the respondents, further research is needed to ascertain whether those changes in attitude can be lasting, especially once the participants returned home. Moreover, direct observations would be needed in order to ascertain whether the sociolinguistic awareness that they developed truly translated into reduced struggles and anxiety in their daily lives. Nonetheless, the data suggests that active language use and interaction with alternative language models (e.g., other international, 'non-native' peers and teachers) can greatly improve learners' willingness to partake in the use of the global lingua franca.

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